

IMPACT OF INTERACTIVE TEACHING TECHNIQUES ON MATHEMATICS COMPREHENSION SKILLS AMONG JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS AT SULU STATE COLLEGE

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Impact of Interactive Teaching Techniques on Mathematics Comprehension Skills Among Junior High School Students at Sulu State College

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Abstract. This study was carried out to measure the impact of the use of interactive teaching techniques on math's comprehension skills of junior high school students at Sulu State College Laboratory High School. A descriptive correlational design of research was used and involved 116 purposively chosen students from Grades 7 to 10 in School Year 2025-2026. The study aimed to scrutinize the impact of interactive teaching techniques in terms of critical thinking skills, interest, and anxiety and stress level in the light of demographic profiles of the respondents (age, gender, grade, educational background of the parents and average monthly income of the parents). Findings indicated that most respondents were in 13-14 years old, female students slightly outnumbering their male counterparts, and the respondents were almost evenly distributed across grade level. Most of the students were from families with college to post-graduate educational backgrounds, however, a sizeable proportion came from low-to-middle income households. Results revealed that students agreed that interactive teaching techniques had positive impact on critical thinking skills and interest in mathematics and induced manageable levels of anxiety and stress while learning in an interactive learning activity. There were no significant differences in responses to the questions when respondents were categorized based on age, gender, educational attainment of parents and average monthly income of parents; however, there were significant differences in responses between grade level, pointing to differences in the experience of the form of interactions when students move up through the grades and become more advanced academically. Moreover, a strong positive correlation between critical thinking skills and interest was found; however, significant relationship between anxiety and stress level and the other dimensions were not found. Based on the findings, it is suggested that school administrators of Sulu State College may lead to strengthening the professional development programs on the effective use of interactive teaching techniques in all grade levels. Mathematics educators can possibly still integrate collaborative, hands-on and student-centered learning strategies to foster comprehension and engagement and learner anxiety management. Students might be actively engaged in the interactive activities maximizing learning benefits also in the future might investigate longitudinal or experimental studies investigating the long-term effects of interactive teaching techniques on mathematics learning outcomes even more.

Keywords: Anxiety and stress level, critical thinking skills, interactive teaching techniques, interest, Mathematics understanding skills

Introduction

Mathematics is perceived as hard, but it is essential for the academic development of the junior high students. While lecture-based teaching has been the primary approach to teaching, the changing pedagogy focuses on interactive techniques that engage learners actively and positively impact outcomes (Afzal & Rafiq, 2022). These strategies (for example discussions, group tasks, simulations, case studies, open-ended questions, problem-solving) encourage participation, collaboration and critical thinking which allow the student to construct understanding rather than receive information passively (Rafiq et al., 2022).

In the Philippines, mathematics is one of the major instructional priorities: DepEd provides an allotted time of about 50 minutes a day (RBEC) or one hour for four days a week (K-12), and math plays a pivotal role in the national assessment such as the NCAE and NAT. To enhance proficiency and, especially, collaboration, schools conduct enrichment programs such as MTAP and the Mathematics Trainers guild. Yet persistent challenges remain - many students still perceived mathematics as complex and abstract and this contributed to poor performance and declining levels of motivation in spite of these initiatives.

International results/standards highlight the challenge: From TIMSS 2003 the Philippines ranked 23/25 (Grade 4) and 41/45 (Grade 8): TIMSS 2000: 36/38 in science and math: PISA 2018: 2nd worst in math with 353 compared to the 489 international averages. These results indicated that there was a need for changes to instruction that enhance critical thinking, increase interest, and reduce anxiety/stress. Accordingly, teachers are using interactive, technology-aided methods for fostering active learning, problem-solving and confidence: stepping away from content delivery and towards a learner-centered, low-stress environment facilitated through deeper understanding of mathematical teachings.

Interactive teaching techniques encourages students in learning mathematics via active involvement in mathematics instead of passive listening involving games, manipulatives and digital tools and assistance for gaining understanding by involving in meaningful experiences (Afzal & Rafiq, 2022). These approaches included collaboration, problem-solving and real-time feedback - elements that are associated with improved comprehension and retention (Rafiq et al., 2022). By incorporating activities, technology and peer learning teachers transform abstract concepts into concrete and accessible that offers multiple pathways for visualizing, discussing and applying new concepts which are eminent of effective active learning (Miller & Redman, 2021; Prince, 2004).

The MATATAG Curriculum promotes interactive, student-centered and competency-based teaching instead of rote memorization in order to develop critical thinking and problem-solving through hands-on, collaborative and real-world tasks (Department of Education, 2023). By actively involving learners, it enhances the level of interest/motivation (Afzal & Rafiq, 2022) and helps to reduce mathematics anxiety and stress because supportive and participatory classes help build confidence and understanding (Yüksel & Geban, 2019). Overall, MATATAG is focused on an environment that is interactive, inclusive, promotes both academic success and emotional well-being as well as long lasting appreciation of mathematics.

In Southwestern Mindanao, Sulu State College is strengthening instructional quality. Specifically, the teachers at Sulu State College Laboratory High School are now practicing the guide of MATATAG curriculum. MATATAG implementation began with Grade 7 in SY 2024–2025 and expanded to Grade 8 in SY 2025–2026. Hence, to help the junior high school of Sulu State College the teachers are adopting new approaches, interactive teaching techniques to develop the students' mathematics comprehension skills.

Interactive teaching techniques help with deep understanding and retention of mathematical concepts, including with the students who had mathematics anxiety. By foregrounding student led tasks and real-world applications, they tend to work in the ways of increasing motivation and interest but also providing multiple entry points for learning. Because interactive lessons rely on activities, visuals, manipulatives, and digital tools, they also appeal to a range of preferences in the learning styles of the class members-and improve the classroom climate, which can benefit all students by being more fun and confidence-building-conditions that are likely to help reduce anxiety and stress levels and help sustain engagement as students prepare for the demands of the next grade level.

Situated in this environment, the present study examined the impact of interactive teaching techniques on the knowledge of mathematics comprehension skills among the junior high schoolers at the Sulu State College with a particular focus on critical thinking skills, interest and anxiety/stress level. By exploring these dimensions in conjunction with each other, the research set out to give evidence of what might inform teachers, school leaders and curriculum developers in their choices and how to scale in ways which both help build understanding, as well as build inclusion and help learners thrive.

Despite national reforms, there was minimal empirical evidence in Sulu State College Laboratory High School to the effect of interactive teaching techniques on mathematics comprehension in particularly three critical thinking, interest, and anxiety/stress. This study addressed the gap by making an estimate of the extent of impact of interactive techniques on these dimensions. Accordingly, the following part explained the particular problem this study deals with, guiding questions for research, and the actual scope to which interactive techniques affect the desired outcomes in the target situation.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to determine the impact of interactive teaching techniques on the mathematics comprehension skills of junior high school students at Sulu State College.

Specifically, it addressed the following research questions.

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. Age;
 - 1.2. Gender;
 - 1.3. Grade Level;
 - 1.4. Parents' Educational Attainments; and
 - 1.5. Parents' Average Monthly Income?

2. What is the extent of impact of interactive teaching techniques on mathematics comprehension skills among junior high school students at Sulu State College in terms of:
 - 2.1. Critical Thinking Skills;
 - 2.2. Interest; and
 - 2.3. Anxiety and Stress Level?
3. Is there a significant difference in the extent of impact of interactive teaching techniques on mathematics comprehension skills among junior high school students at Sulu State College when the data are grouped according to:
 - 3.1. Age;
 - 3.2. Gender;
 - 3.3. Grade Level;
 - 3.4. Parents' Educational Attainments; and
 - 3.5. Parents' Average Monthly Income?
4. Is there a significant correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the extent of impact of interactive teaching techniques on mathematics comprehension skills among junior high school students at Sulu State College?

Literature Review

Interactive teaching techniques have become essential in improving mathematics education, particularly in fostering deeper understanding and engagement among learners. Rooted in constructivist learning theory, these approaches emphasize active participation, collaboration, and knowledge construction rather than passive memorization. Hetmanenko (2024) explained that interactive learning environments encourage students to engage in discovery and reflection, leading to more meaningful learning experiences. This aligns with the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) framework, which prioritizes reasoning, problem-solving, and modeling over procedural knowledge. Mathematics comprehension is achieved when students can explain both the processes and underlying concepts of mathematical procedures (Hiebert & Carpenter, 1992). Recent perspectives highlight that comprehension is further strengthened when learners explore multiple strategies, justify their reasoning, and engage in peer discussions (Rohaeti, 2025). Interactive classrooms provide opportunities for such experiences through group work, guided inquiry, and the use of manipulatives. These approaches not only enhance conceptual understanding but also promote knowledge transfer and active participation, particularly among junior high school learners. Interactive teaching also plays a crucial role in developing critical thinking. Dewey (1933) emphasized reflective thinking as central to learning, while Beswick (2023) highlighted the importance of teacher–student interaction in cultivating reasoning skills. Through questioning, collaborative problem-solving, and peer evaluation, students develop higher-order thinking skills and metacognitive awareness. These practices enable learners to view mathematics as a process of reasoning and inquiry rather than mere computation. Motivation and interest are also significantly influenced by interactive teaching. According to Self-Determination Theory (Deci & Ryan, 1985), autonomy, competence, and relatedness foster intrinsic motivation—all of which are present in interactive learning environments. Engaging strategies such as problem-based learning and game-based activities have been shown to increase students' enthusiasm and persistence (Debrenti, 2024). When students find learning meaningful and enjoyable, they are more likely to remain engaged and achieve better outcomes. Furthermore, interactive teaching helps reduce mathematics anxiety. Pekrun's (2006) control-value theory suggests that students experience less anxiety when they feel in control of their learning and perceive tasks as valuable. Interactive environments promote collaboration, feedback, and open communication, which reduce fear of failure and encourage confidence (Rohaeti, 2025). As a result, students become more willing to participate and take intellectual risks.

Numerous studies have confirmed the effectiveness of interactive teaching in enhancing mathematical reasoning and comprehension. Taja-on (2021) and Applebaum (2025) found that game-based learning improves analytical thinking, motivation, and problem-solving skills. Similarly, Supriadi (2024) and Sosa-Gutiérrez et al. (2024) emphasized that inquiry-based and digital interactive approaches strengthen reasoning, conceptual understanding, and student engagement. While some studies highlight the role of technology, others focus on dialogue and reflection, yet all agree that interactivity promotes active learning. Cooperative and discussion-based learning also contribute significantly to cognitive development. Kamran et al. (2023) and Sachdeva (2021) demonstrated that collaborative learning and reflective dialogue enhance analytical thinking, metacognition, and knowledge retention. These findings suggest that interaction—whether through peer collaboration or guided reflection—supports deeper comprehension. Interactive teaching is also linked to increased student interest. Studies by Hetmanenko et al. (2024), Tukiman et al. (2024), and Lubis et al. (2023) show that interactive activities, including games and digital tools, increase motivation, curiosity, and persistence. These approaches transform mathematics into an engaging subject, encouraging students to explore concepts actively. In addition, research highlights the role of interactivity in reducing anxiety. Barroso et al. (2020) found that mathematics anxiety negatively affects performance, while Ma (2025) and Ersözülü (2024) showed that interactive and concept-based instruction reduces stress by

promoting understanding and providing supportive learning environments. These studies emphasize that both cognitive and emotional factors are critical in mathematics learning.

Local studies in the Philippine context support these findings. Lomibao (2016) and Bautista (2021) demonstrated that lesson study and improved teacher questioning enhance students' problem-solving and reasoning skills. Similarly, Dicediquin (2023) and UP NISMED (2024) found that professional development and collaborative teaching practices promote student-centered learning and richer classroom discussions. Technology integration has also been shown to improve learning outcomes. Anario (2022) and Pospos and Piñero (2024) reported that GeoGebra and other digital tools enhance students' conceptual understanding, reasoning, and engagement. These tools allow learners to explore mathematical concepts dynamically, making abstract ideas more concrete and accessible. Moreover, contextualized and inquiry-based approaches have been found to increase student interest and participation. Santos (2015) highlighted that mathematical modeling improves problem-solving skills and reduces anxiety by connecting lessons to real-life situations. Similarly, guided inquiry approaches during remote learning-maintained student engagement and supported reasoning through structured interaction. Mathematics anxiety remains a concern in local contexts. Delgado (2019) and Padlan (2023) found that anxiety negatively affects academic performance among Filipino students. However, interactive teaching strategies—such as collaborative learning, formative assessment, and conceptual instruction—have been shown to reduce anxiety and improve confidence. These findings suggest that supportive and engaging learning environments are essential in addressing both cognitive and emotional challenges in mathematics education.

Methodology

Research Design

This study was carried out in descriptive-correlational design which was used to explore the impact of interactive teaching techniques on mathematics comprehension skills among junior high school students in Sulu State College Laboratory High School. The three characteristics that were explored in this research were critical thinking skills, interest, stress level and anxiety. According to McCurney and White (2009) as referenced by Ivy Panda (2023), descriptive-correlational design is used during research investigations that want to find the connection among variables and depict static scenarios of settings.

Sampling Design

In this research, the researchers used a purposive sampling for the selection of the respondents. It is used to select respondents that are most likely to yield appropriate and useful information (Kelly, 2010) and is a way of identifying and selecting cases that would use limited research resources effectively (Palinkas et al, 2015).

Research Participants

The study involved a total of 116 junior high school students, selected from a population of 561 students at Sulu State College Laboratory High School who were officially enrolled in the academic year 2025–2026. The respondents were distributed across grades 7 to 10, with each grade consisting of three sections. Each section contributed 9 to 10 students to the sample, ensuring proportional representation across all grade levels.

Research Instruments

This study utilized a survey questionnaire in checklist format, adopted and revised from the instruments developed by Vizcayno (2023) and Montaña (2018) that measured the effectiveness of interactive teaching techniques on students' mathematics comprehension skills. The questionnaire consisted of two parts: Part one collected the respondents' personal data, while Part two assessed three subcategories of interactive teaching techniques—critical thinking skills, interest, and stress/anxiety levels. Responses were recorded using a 5-point Likert scale, with the options Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Undecided (U), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD), corresponding to the rating intervals 1.00–1.49 (Strongly Disagree) up to 4.50–5.00 (Strongly Agree).

Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers obtained a letter of permission from Dean's Office of Graduate Studies for the launching of the questionnaire. After obtaining the letter of permission from the Dean's Office of Graduate Studies, the researchers proceeded straight to the Office of the President at Sulu State College to obtain the letter of approval. After getting approval from the concerned authority at Sulu State College to administer the instrument, the researchers presented the approved letter to Sulu State College Laboratory High School Principal to inform him of the data for the study to be collected. Then the principal agreed and allowed the researchers to administer the instruments to the sample respondents. The questionnaire was retrieved on the same day.

Results and Discussion

Problem 1: What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, gender, grade level, parents' educational attainments, and parents' average monthly income?

Table 1.1: Demographic Profile of Students at Sulu State College Laboratory High School by Age

Age	Number of respondents	Percent
12 years old and below	36	31.0%
13-14 years old	46	39.7%
15 years old and above	34	29.3%
Total	116	100%

Table 1.1 presents the demographic profile of students at Sulu State College Laboratory High School in terms of age. The data indicated that out of 116 respondents, 36 students (31% or 31.0%) lie in the age group of 12 and below, 46 students belong to the age group of 13-14 years and 34 students belong to the age group of 15 years and above. These results showed that the maximum proportion of the respondents fall under the age bracket of 13-14 years which amounts to nearly two-fifths of the total sample. This age distribution indicated that the majority of the respondents was in the early to middle adolescent level that was common in junior high school which was the age of the students that were suitable for the learners that were enrolled at Sulu State College Laboratory High School.

Table 1.2: Demographic Profile of Students in terms of Gender

Gender	Number of respondents	Percent
Male	51	44.0%
Female	65	56.0%
Total	116	100%

Table 1.2 shows the demographic profile of the students at Sulu State College Laboratory High School according to the gender. The data showed out of a total sample of 116 respondents 51 students were males which is 44.0%, and 65 students were females which is 56.0%. These findings revealed that the female students slightly outnumbered the male students as they comprised of more than half of the total respondents. This distribution of the two genders indicated a fairly balanced representation of male and female learners with a slight predominance of female learners.

Table 1.3: Demographic Profile of Students in terms of Grade Level

Grade Level	Number of respondents	Percent
Grade 7	30	25.9%
Grade 8	30	25.9%
Grade 9	27	23.3%
Grade 10	29	25.0%
Total	116	100%

Table 1.3 shows the demographic profile of the students from Sulu State College Laboratory High School according to grade level. The data showed out of 116 respondents, 30 students came from Grade 7 (25.9%), 30 students came from Grade 8 (25.9%), 27 students came from Grade 9 (23.3%) and 29 students came from Grade 10 (25.0%). The distribution illustrated that the respondents were distributed almost equally in all grade levels and there were minimal variations in the percentages.

Table 1.4. Demographic Profile of Students in terms of Parents' Educational Attainment

Parents' Educational Attainment	Number of respondents	Percent
No Formal Education	1	.9%
Elementary Level	5	4.3%
High School Level	18	15.5%
College Level	40	34.5%
Post-graduate Level	52	44.8%
Total	116	100%

Table 1.4 provides the demographic information of students at Sulu State College Laboratory High School concerning the educational attainment of their parents. The data result revealed that out of 116 respondents, 1 student (0.9%) indicated that their parents had no formal education, 5 students (4.3%) had parents with an elementary education, and 18 students (15.5%) had parents who achieved the high school level. Meanwhile, the bigger percentage of the respondents in a classified education were higher school of education where 40 students (34.5%) indicated college level education while 52 students (44.8%) indicated post-graduate level education. These results indicated that the majority of the respondents were from

families with relatively high educational background, which could have positively affected the support of these students for their academics and their learning attitude to study mathematics.

Table 1.5: Demographic Profile of Students in terms of Parents' Average Monthly Income

Parents' Average Monthly Income	Number of respondents	Percent
5000 pesos and below	45	38.8%
5,001 – 10,000 pesos	41	35.3%
10,001 pesos and above	30	25.9%
Total	116	100%

Table 1.5 presents the demographic profile of the students in Sulu State College Laboratory High School in terms of the average monthly income of their parents. The data showed that out of 116 respondents, 45 students (38,8%) were from families with an income of 5,000 pesos and below while 41 students (35.3%) reported a monthly income of 5,001-10,000 pesos. Meanwhile, 30 students (25.9%) belonged to the family with a monthly income of 10,001 pesos and above. These results indicated that there was a significant proportion of students who came from low to middle-income households, meaning that there was a range in the socioeconomic background of the students.

Problem 2: What is the extent of impact of interactive teaching techniques to mathematics comprehension skills among junior high school students at Sulu State College in terms of critical thinking skills, interest, and anxiety and stress level?

Table 2.1: Extent of Impact of Interactive Teaching Techniques on Mathematics Comprehension Skills Among the Students in Terms of Critical Thinking Skills

Statements	Mean	SD	Rating
1 I can effectively apply problem-solving strategies when working on interactive mathematics tasks.	3.25	.922	Partially Agree
2 I can describe how interactive learning strategies help me understand and retain mathematical concepts.	3.73	.926	Agree
3 I find myself thinking critically and analytically when engaged in interactive mathematics activities.	3.91	.840	Agree
4 I can integrate new mathematical knowledge with previously learned concepts during interactive learning sessions.	3.44	.989	Partially Agree
5 I can make connections between mathematical concepts and real-world applications through interactive learning experiences.	3.47	.999	Partially Agree
6 I feel challenged to think creatively and explore different problem-solving approaches during interactive mathematics tasks.	3.75	1.046	Agree
7 I use interactive learning strategies to enhance my ability to visualize and manipulate mathematical representations, such as graphs or diagrams.	3.51	1.017	Agree
8 I can explain how interactive mathematics activities promote my active engagement and sustained attention to mathematical tasks.	3.40	1.003	Partially Agree
9 I can independently explore and investigate mathematical concepts further during interactive learning sessions.	3.13	1.059	Partially Agree
10 I use interactive learning strategies to support my development of metacognitive skills, such as self-monitoring and reflection, in mathematics.	3.62	.939	Agree
Total Weighted Mean	3.52	.60383	Agree

Table 2.1 presented the extent of the impact of interactive teaching techniques on mathematics comprehension skills among junior high school students at Sulu State College Laboratory High School in terms of critical thinking skills. The results showed a total weighted mean of 3.52 with a standard deviation of 0.60, which corresponded to an overall rating of "Agree." This indicated that students generally perceived interactive teaching techniques as effective in enhancing their critical thinking skills in mathematics. Among the indicators, the highest-rated statement was "I find myself thinking critically and analytically when engaged in interactive mathematics activities" with a mean of 3.91 (Agree). This suggested that interactive mathematics activities encouraged students to analyze problems, evaluate solutions, and engage in higher-order thinking processes. Similarly, the statements "I feel challenged to think creatively and explore different problem-solving approaches during interactive mathematics tasks" ($\bar{x} = 3.75$) and "I can describe how interactive learning strategies help me understand and retain mathematical concepts" ($\bar{x} = 3.73$) were also rated Agree, indicating that interactive strategies supported both conceptual understanding and creative reasoning. In contrast, the lowest-rated statement was "I can independently explore and investigate mathematical concepts further during interactive learning sessions" with a mean of 3.13 (Partially Agree). This implied that although interactive teaching techniques promoted critical thinking, students might still

have relied on teacher guidance and structured activities to fully develop independent inquiry skills. Other statements related to integrating prior knowledge, real-world application, and sustained attention were likewise rated Partially Agree, suggesting areas for further instructional enhancement. Overall, the findings indicated that interactive teaching techniques positively influenced students' critical thinking skills, particularly in analysis, creativity, and conceptual understanding. Press (2023) reported that teaching strategies involving problem solving, discussion, and active engagement were strongly associated with improved critical thinking skills in mathematics.

Table 2.2: Extent of Impact of Interactive Teaching Techniques on Mathematics Comprehension Skills Among the Students in Terms of Interest

	Statements	Mean	SD	Rating
1	I actively participate in group discussions and collaborative problem-solving activities during mathematics lessons.	3.56	1.129	Agree
2	I eagerly volunteer to demonstrate mathematical concepts or solutions to the class during interactive learning sessions.	3.00	1.142	Partially Agree
3	I regularly seek assistance from my teacher or peers when encountering challenging mathematical problems.	3.68	1.206	Agree
4	I demonstrate persistence and resilience when faced with difficult mathematical tasks, actively seeking solutions until I succeed.	3.80	.867	Agree
5	I utilize mathematical tools and technology effectively to enhance my understanding and performance during interactive learning activities.	3.66	.986	Agree
6	I engage in hands-on activities and manipulatives to explore mathematical concepts tangibly.	3.32	.965	Partially Agree
7	I take the initiative to explore additional resources or supplementary materials to deepen my understanding of mathematical topics.	3.73	.926	Agree
8	I actively contribute to collaborative projects and group presentations on mathematical concepts and applications.	3.80	.989	Agree
9	I actively participate in peer tutoring or mentoring activities to support my classmates' understanding of mathematical concepts.	3.32	1.076	Partially Agree
10	I demonstrate responsible behavior by completing assigned mathematics tasks on time and following classroom rules and expectations during interactive learning sessions.	3.84	1.038	Agree
	Total Weighted Mean	3.57	.63763	Agree

Table 2.2 presented the extent of the impact of interactive teaching techniques on mathematics comprehension skills among junior high school students at Sulu State College Laboratory High School in terms of interest. The results revealed a total weighted mean of 3.57 with a standard deviation of 0.64, which corresponded to an overall rating of "Agree." This indicated that students generally perceived interactive teaching techniques as effective in increasing their interest and engagement in learning mathematics. Among the indicators, the highest-rated statements were "I demonstrate responsible behavior by completing assigned mathematics tasks on time and following classroom rules and expectations during interactive learning sessions" ($\bar{x} = 3.84$) and "I demonstrate persistence and resilience when faced with difficult mathematical tasks" as well as "I actively contribute to collaborative projects and group presentations" (both $\bar{x} = 3.80$), all interpreted as Agree. These findings suggested that interactive teaching techniques encouraged positive learning behaviors such as persistence, collaboration, and responsibility, which were essential components of sustained interest in mathematics. Other statements related to seeking assistance ($\bar{x} = 3.68$), effective use of tools and technology ($\bar{x} = 3.66$), and initiative in exploring additional learning resources ($\bar{x} = 3.73$) were likewise rated Agree, indicating that interactive learning environments promoted help-seeking behavior, autonomy, and active engagement. However, relatively lower ratings were observed for "I eagerly volunteer to demonstrate mathematical concepts or solutions to the class" ($\bar{x} = 3.00$) and "I actively participate in peer tutoring or mentoring activities" ($\bar{x} = 3.32$), both interpreted as Partially Agree. This implied that while students were generally interested, some might still have experienced hesitation in public performance or peer-led instructional roles. Overall, the findings indicated that interactive teaching techniques positively influenced students' interest in mathematics by fostering engagement, persistence, collaboration, and responsible learning behaviors. Hetmanenko et al. (2024) found that interactive learning environments significantly increased students' interest by making mathematical concepts more meaningful and engaging.

Table 2.3: Extent of Impact of Interactive Teaching Techniques on Mathematics Comprehension Skills Among the Students in Terms of Anxiety and Stress Level

	Statements	Mean	SD	Rating
1	My heart races when I'm asked to explain a mathematics solution in class.	3.84	1.251	Agree
2	I worry about making mistakes during interactive math activities (e.g., group problem-solving, games).	4.19	.995	Agree
3	I feel tense when starting a new or complex mathematics task, even with guidance.	3.56	1.121	Agree

4	Time-limited math activities make me feel overwhelmed.	3.82	1.154	Agree
5	I find it hard to concentrate on math when classmates are watching me work.	3.45	1.347	Partially Agree
6	I feel stressed by the amount of work expected during interactive mathematics lessons.	3.49	1.107	Partially Agree
7	I avoid volunteering answers in math because I'm afraid of being wrong.	3.19	1.426	Partially Agree
8	After math class, I still feel anxious about what we covered.	3.00	1.272	Partially Agree
9	I feel calm and in control during interactive mathematics activities. (reverse-coded)	3.22	1.037	Partially Agree
10	I can quickly relax after struggling with a math problem. (reverse-coded)	3.55	1.175	Agree
Total Weighted Mean		3.53	.72210	Agree

Table 2.3 presented the extent of the impact of interactive teaching techniques on mathematics comprehension skills among junior high school students at Sulu State College Laboratory High School in terms of anxiety and stress level. The results showed a total weighted mean of 3.53 with a standard deviation of 0.72, corresponding to an overall rating of “Agree.” This indicated that students generally experienced noticeable levels of anxiety and stress during interactive mathematics activities, suggesting that while interactive teaching promoted engagement, it might also have elicited emotional pressure in certain learning situations. Among the indicators, the highest-rated statement was “I worry about making mistakes during interactive math activities” with a mean of 4.19 (Agree). This finding suggested that fear of errors remained a prominent source of anxiety among students, particularly in collaborative and performance-based tasks. Other statements such as “My heart races when I’m asked to explain a mathematics solution in class” ($\bar{x} = 3.84$) and “Time-limited math activities make me feel overwhelmed” ($\bar{x} = 3.82$) were also rated Agree, indicating that public explanation and time pressure contributed significantly to students’ stress levels. In contrast, several indicators were rated Partially Agree, including difficulty concentrating when being observed by classmates ($\bar{x} = 3.45$), stress due to workload ($\bar{x} = 3.49$), and avoidance of volunteering answers because of fear of being wrong ($\bar{x} = 3.19$). The reverse-coded items “I feel calm and in control during interactive mathematics activities” ($\bar{x} = 3.22$) and “I can quickly relax after struggling with a math problem” ($\bar{x} = 3.55$, Agree) suggested that although students experienced anxiety, many were still able to regain emotional control after encountering difficulty. Overall, the findings indicated that interactive teaching techniques might have simultaneously engaged students and evoked anxiety, particularly in situations involving peer observation, time constraints, and public performance. Barroso et al. (2020) found that fear of making mistakes and performance pressure were strong predictors of mathematics anxiety. Similarly, Ersözlü (2024) reported that while interactive and technology-based mathematics instruction could reduce anxiety, poorly structured or highly competitive activities might increase stress.

Problem 3: Is there a significant difference in the extent of impact of interactive teaching techniques on mathematics comprehension skills among junior high school students at Sulu State College when the data are grouped according to age, gender, grade level, parents’ educational attainments, and parents’ average monthly income?

Table 3.1: Difference in the Extent of Impact of Interactive Teaching Techniques on Mathematics Comprehension Skills Among the Students When the Data are Grouped According to Age

Sources of Variation		Sum of squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Critical Thinking Skills	Between Groups	.096	2	.048	.130	.878	Not Significant
	Within Groups	41.83	113	.370			
	Total	41.93	115				
Interest	Between Groups	.591	2	.295	.723	.487	Not Significant
	Within Groups	46.16	113	.409			
	Total	46.75	115				
Anxiety and Stress Level	Between Groups	.183	2	.092	.173	.841	Not Significant
	Within Groups	59.78	113	.529			
	Total	59.96	115				

Note. * Significant at alpha 0.05

Table 3.1 presented the differences in the extent of impact of interactive teaching techniques on mathematics comprehension skills among junior high school students at Sulu State College Laboratory High School when the data were grouped according to age. The table showed the computed F-values and corresponding significance (Sig.) values for the three dimensions of mathematics comprehension skills, namely critical thinking skills, interest, and anxiety and stress level. For critical thinking skills, the computed F-value was 0.130 with a Sig. value of 0.878, which was higher than the alpha level of 0.05. This indicated that there was no significant difference in the extent of impact of interactive teaching techniques on students’ critical thinking skills when grouped according to age. In terms of interest, the results revealed an F-value of 0.723 and a Sig. value of 0.487, which was likewise greater than 0.05. This suggested that students’ level of

interest in mathematics under interactive teaching techniques did not significantly vary across different age groups. Similarly, for anxiety and stress level, the obtained F-value was 0.173 with a Sig. value of 0.841, indicating no significant difference among students of different ages. This implied that students' experiences of anxiety and stress during interactive mathematics activities were comparable regardless of age. The findings revealed that age did not significantly influence the extent of impact of interactive teaching techniques on mathematics comprehension skills across all three dimensions. Hence, the null hypothesis, which stated that "There is no significant difference in the extent of impact of interactive teaching techniques on mathematics comprehension skills among junior high school students at Sulu State College when the data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of age," was accepted.

Table 3.2: Difference in the Extent of Impact of Interactive Teaching Techniques on Mathematics Comprehension Skills Among the Students When the Data are Grouped According to Gender

Variables	Grouping	Mean	SD	Mean Difference	T	Sig.	Description
Critical Thinking Skills	Male	3.586	.5040	.11704	1.072	.286	Not Significant
	Female	3.469	.6713				
Interest	Male	3.690	.4776	.21173	1.882	.063	Not Significant
	Female	3.479	.7296				
Anxiety and Stress Level	Male	3.390	.7297	-.24980	-1.87	.064	Not Significant
	Female	3.640	.7022				

Note. * Significant at alpha 0.05

Table 3.2 presented the difference in the extent of impact of interactive teaching techniques on mathematics comprehension skills among junior high school students at Sulu State College Laboratory High School when the data were grouped according to gender. The table showed the computed mean scores, t-values, and corresponding significance (Sig.) values for critical thinking skills, interest, and anxiety and stress level. For critical thinking skills, male students obtained a mean score of 3.586 (SD = 0.5040), while female students obtained a mean score of 3.469 (SD = 0.6713). The computed t-value was 1.072 with a Sig. value of 0.286, which was greater than the alpha level of 0.05. This indicated that there was no significant difference in the extent of impact of interactive teaching techniques on critical thinking skills between male and female students. In terms of interest, male students recorded a mean of 3.690 (SD = 0.4776), while female students had a mean of 3.479 (SD = 0.7296). The obtained t-value of 1.882 with a Sig. value of 0.063 was also higher than 0.05, indicating no significant difference in students' interest in mathematics under interactive teaching techniques when grouped by gender. Similarly, for anxiety and stress level, male students had a mean score of 3.390 (SD = 0.7297) compared to 3.640 (SD = 0.7022) for female students. The computed t-value was -1.87 with a Sig. value of 0.064, which was likewise greater than the 0.05 significance level. This suggested that the level of anxiety and stress experienced by students during interactive mathematics activities did not significantly differ between male and female students. The findings indicated that gender did not significantly influence the extent of impact of interactive teaching techniques on mathematics comprehension skills across the three dimensions. Thus, the null hypothesis, which stated that "There is no significant difference in the extent of impact of interactive teaching techniques on mathematics comprehension skills among junior high school students at Sulu State College when the data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of gender," was accepted.

Table 3.3: Difference in the Extent of Impact of Interactive Teaching Techniques on Mathematics Comprehension Skills Among the Students at Sulu State College When the Data are Grouped According to Grade Level

Sources of Variation		Sum of squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Critical Thinking Skills	Between Groups	2.882	3	.961	2.75	.046*	Significant
	Within Groups	39.05	112	.349			
	Total	41.93	115				
Interest	Between Groups	5.968	3	1.989	5.46	.002*	Significant
	Within Groups	40.78	112	.364			
	Total	46.75	115				
Anxiety and Stress Level	Between Groups	8.747	3	2.916	6.37	.000*	Significant
	Within Groups	51.21	112	.457			
	Total	59.96	115				

Note. * Significant at alpha 0.05

Table 3.3 presented the differences in the extent of impact of interactive teaching techniques on mathematics comprehension skills among junior high school students at Sulu State College Laboratory High School when the data were grouped according to grade level. The table showed the computed F-values and corresponding significance (Sig.) values for the three dimensions of mathematics comprehension skills, namely critical thinking skills, interest, and anxiety and stress level. For critical thinking skills, the analysis yielded an F-value of 2.755 with a Sig. value of 0.046, which was less than the alpha level of 0.05. This indicated that there was a significant difference in the extent of impact of interactive teaching techniques on

students' critical thinking skills when grouped according to grade level. This suggested that students' critical thinking development through interactive teaching techniques varied across different junior high school grade levels. In terms of interest, the computed F-value was 5.462 with a Sig. value of 0.002, which was likewise lower than 0.05. This result indicated a significant difference in students' interest in mathematics under interactive teaching techniques across grade levels, implying that students' level of engagement and enthusiasm in interactive mathematics activities differed depending on their grade level. Similarly, for anxiety and stress level, the obtained F-value of 6.376 with a Sig. value of 0.000 showed a highly significant difference among grade levels. This suggested that students experienced varying levels of anxiety and stress during interactive mathematics activities as they progressed through different grade levels. The findings revealed that grade level significantly influenced the extent of impact of interactive teaching techniques on mathematics comprehension skills across all three dimensions. Hence, the null hypothesis, which stated that "There is no significant difference in the extent of impact of interactive teaching techniques on mathematics comprehension skills among junior high school students at Sulu State College when the data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of grade level," was rejected.

Table 3.3.1: Multiple Comparison in the Extent of Impact of Interactive Teaching Techniques on Mathematics Comprehension Skills Among the Students When the Data are Grouped According to Grade Level

Dependent Variable	(I) Grouping by Year Level	(J) Grouping by Year Level	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Critical Thinking Skills	Grade 8	Grade 9	.42148*	.15664	.040
	Grade 9	Grade 7	-.42593*	.16009	.044
Interest	Grade 8	Grade 9	-.63926*	.16009	.001
	Grade 8	Grade 9	.77815*	.17939	.000

Note. * The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level

Table 3.3.1 presents the Post Hoc Analysis examining pairwise differences in the extent of impact of interactive teaching techniques on mathematics comprehension skills among junior high school students at Sulu State College Laboratory High School across grade levels. The results revealed significant differences in critical thinking skills, interest, and anxiety and stress levels. Specifically, Grade 8 students demonstrated significantly higher critical thinking skills than Grade 9 students (mean difference = 0.42148, $p = 0.040$). In terms of interest, Grade 7 students showed significantly higher interest than Grade 9 students (mean difference = -0.42593 , $p = 0.044$), while Grade 8 students also exhibited significantly higher interest compared to Grade 9 students (mean difference = -0.63926 , $p = 0.001$). For anxiety and stress levels, Grade 8 students experienced significantly higher levels compared to Grade 9 students (mean difference = 0.77815 , $p < 0.001$). These findings indicate that the effectiveness of interactive teaching techniques on mathematics comprehension skills varies across grade levels, affecting students' critical thinking, interest, and anxiety differently.

Table 3.4: Difference in the Extent of Impact of Interactive Teaching Techniques on Mathematics Comprehension Skills Among the Students When the Data are Grouped According to Parents' Educational Attainment

Sources of Variation		Sum of squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Critical Thinking Skills	Between Groups	2.601	4	.650	1.83	.127	Not Significant
	Within Groups	39.33	111	.354			
	Total	41.93	115				
Interest	Between Groups	2.561	4	.640	1.60	.177	Not Significant
	Within Groups	44.19	111	.398			
	Total	46.75	115				
Anxiety and Stress Level	Between Groups	1.286	4	.321	.608	.658	Not Significant
	Within Groups	58.67	111	.529			
	Total	59.96	115				

Note. * Significant at alpha 0.05

Table 3.4 presented the differences in the extent of impact of interactive teaching techniques on mathematics comprehension skills among junior high school students at Sulu State College Laboratory High School when the data were grouped according to parents' educational attainment. The table showed the computed F-values and corresponding significance (Sig.) values for the three dimensions of mathematics comprehension skills, namely critical thinking skills, interest, and anxiety and stress level. For critical thinking skills, the analysis yielded an F-value of 1.835 with a Sig. value of 0.127, which was greater than the alpha level of 0.05. This indicated that there was no significant difference in the extent of impact of interactive teaching techniques on students' critical thinking skills when grouped according to parents' educational attainment. In terms of interest, the computed F-value was 1.608 with a Sig. value of 0.177, which was likewise higher than 0.05. This result suggested that students' interest in mathematics under interactive teaching techniques did not significantly vary based on their parents' educational attainment. Similarly, for anxiety and stress level, the obtained F-value of 0.608 with a Sig. value of 0.658 indicated no significant difference among students from different parental educational backgrounds. The findings

revealed that parents' educational attainment did not significantly influence the extent of impact of interactive teaching techniques on mathematics comprehension skills across all three dimensions. Hence, the null hypothesis, which stated that "There is no significant difference in the extent of impact of interactive teaching techniques on mathematics comprehension skills among junior high school students at Sulu State College when the data were grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of parents' educational attainment," was accepted.

Table 3.5: Difference in the Extent of Impact of Interactive Teaching Techniques on Mathematics Comprehension Skills Among the Students When the Data are Grouped According to Parents' Average Monthly Income

Sources of Variation		Sum of squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Critical Thinking Skills	Between Groups	2.151	2	1.075	3.05	.051	Not Significant
	Within Groups	39.78	113	.352			
	Total	41.93	115				
Interest	Between Groups	2.091	2	1.045	2.64	.075	Not Significant
	Within Groups	44.66	113	.395			
	Total	46.75	115				
Anxiety and Stress Level	Between Groups	.105	2	.052	.099	.906	Not Significant
	Within Groups	59.85	113	.530			
	Total	59.96	115				

Note. * Significant at alpha 0.05

Table 3.5 presented the differences in the extent of impact of interactive teaching techniques on mathematics comprehension skills among junior high school students at Sulu State College Laboratory High School when the data were grouped according to parents' average monthly income. The table showed the computed F-values and corresponding significance (Sig.) values for the three dimensions of mathematics comprehension skills, namely critical thinking skills, interest, and anxiety and stress level. For critical thinking skills, the analysis yielded an F-value of 3.055 with a Sig. value of 0.051, which was slightly higher than the alpha level of 0.05. This indicated that there was no significant difference in the extent of impact of interactive teaching techniques on students' critical thinking skills when grouped according to parents' average monthly income. In terms of interest, the computed F-value was 2.644 with a Sig. value of 0.075, which was likewise greater than 0.05. This suggested that students' level of interest in mathematics under interactive teaching techniques did not significantly vary across different income groups. Similarly, for anxiety and stress level, the obtained F-value of 0.099 with a Sig. value of 0.906 indicated no significant difference among students from different parental income levels. The findings revealed that parents' average monthly income did not significantly influence the extent of impact of interactive teaching techniques on mathematics comprehension skills across all three dimensions. Hence, the null hypothesis, which stated that "There is no significant difference in the extent of impact of interactive teaching techniques on mathematics comprehension skills among junior high school students at Sulu State College when the data were grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of parents' average monthly income," was accepted.

Problem 4: Is there a significant correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the extent of impact of interactive teaching techniques on mathematics comprehension skills among junior high school students at Sulu State College?

Table 4: Correlations Among the Sub-Categories Subsumed Under the Extent of Impact of Interactive Teaching Techniques on Mathematics Comprehension Skills Among the Students

Variables		Pearson r	Sig.	N	Description
Dependent	Independent				
Critical Thinking Skills	Interest	.775**	.000	116	High
Critical Thinking Skills	Anxiety and Stress Level	.008	.930	116	No Correlation
Interest	Anxiety and Stress Level	.121	.196	116	No Correlation

Note. **Correlation coefficient is significant at alpha .01

Table 4 shows the correlations among the sub-categories measuring the impact of interactive teaching techniques on mathematics comprehension skills among 116 junior high school students at Sulu State College Laboratory High School. The results indicated a strong positive and statistically significant relationship between critical thinking skills and interest ($r = 0.775$, $p < 0.01$), suggesting that students who were more interested in interactive mathematics activities also demonstrated higher critical thinking skills. However, no significant correlations were found between critical thinking skills and anxiety and stress level ($r = 0.008$, $p = 0.930$) or between interest and anxiety and stress level ($r = 0.121$, $p = 0.196$), indicating that anxiety and stress operated independently of both critical thinking and interest. Overall, while interest and critical thinking skills were closely linked, anxiety and stress did not significantly affect these dimensions, supporting the acceptance of the hypothesis that no significant correlations exist among all the sub-categories under the extent of impact of interactive teaching techniques on mathematics comprehension skills.

Ethical Considerations

The study adhered strictly to recognized ethical guidelines to ensure the reliability, validity, and integrity of the research process. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, who were fully aware of the study's purpose, procedures, and scope, and were free to withdraw at any time without penalty. Participants' confidentiality and anonymity were maintained, with no identifying information disclosed in reports or publications. Participation was entirely voluntary, without coercion or undue influence. The integrity of data was upheld, with all information gathered, recorded, analyzed, and reported truthfully, avoiding any form of fabrication, falsification, or misrepresentation. The researchers respected the rights, dignity, and welfare of participants, valuing their views and experiences throughout the study. The study was conducted with beneficence and non-maleficence in mind, ensuring no physical, psychological, or social harm came to participants. Furthermore, the research complied with the ethical policies of the School of Graduate Studies, Sulu State College (SSC), as well as national and international standards for educational research. Prior to data collection, ethical clearance was secured from the Research Ethics Committee of SSC to guarantee adherence to institutional and professional ethical standards.

Conclusion

The study concludes that junior high school students at Sulu State College Laboratory High School represent a diverse and balanced population in terms of age, gender, grade level, and parents' educational attainment and income, supporting the inclusiveness and generalizability of the findings. Interactive teaching techniques were found to have a positive and meaningful effect on students' mathematics comprehension skills, particularly in enhancing critical thinking and interest. While students reported experiencing some anxiety and stress, these emotions did not significantly undermine comprehension, indicating that interactive strategies can provide productive challenges rather than undue pressure. The impact of these techniques did not differ significantly across age, gender, or parents' socioeconomic background, but significant differences were observed across grade levels, suggesting that developmental and curricular factors influence how students engage with and benefit from interactive instruction. Moreover, a strong positive association was found between critical thinking skills and interest, highlighting that increased interest in mathematics is accompanied by enhanced analytical and reasoning skills, whereas anxiety and stress appeared independent of cognitive and motivational outcomes. These findings underscore the importance of interactive, student-centered instruction for fostering engagement and higher-order thinking in mathematics while indicating a need for targeted interventions to address students' emotional responses.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, several recommendations are proposed. Policy makers are encouraged to strengthen mathematics education by formulating and supporting policies that promote the use of interactive teaching techniques, with particular attention to strategies that enhance critical thinking, sustain student interest, and address developmental differences across grade levels. School administrators at Sulu State College should provide ongoing professional development programs for mathematics teachers to improve the design and implementation of interactive instruction, especially strategies that foster critical thinking, maintain engagement, and manage anxiety and stress in classrooms of varying grade levels. Mathematics teachers are advised to consistently incorporate student-centered and interactive approaches, such as collaborative problem-solving, hands-on activities, and guided inquiry, to strengthen students' critical thinking skills, sustain interest, and create a supportive classroom environment that minimizes performance-related anxiety. Parents can actively contribute by encouraging positive attitudes toward mathematics, providing emotional support during challenging tasks, and reinforcing curiosity, effort, and persistence at home, irrespective of socioeconomic background. Students are encouraged to actively engage in interactive mathematics activities, including discussions, collaborative work, and problem-solving exercises, while developing self-regulation strategies to manage anxiety and stress and enhance both interest and critical thinking. Finally, future researchers are recommended to explore the longitudinal effects of interactive teaching strategies on mathematics comprehension, particularly examining differences across grade levels in relation to critical thinking, interest, and anxiety.

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